

Appendix E: Quality Evaluation of SLR Studies

Quality Assessment using ROBIS Tool

#	Author's name	Domain 1: Study Eligibility Criteria	Domain 2: Identification and Selection of Studies	Domain 3: Data Collection and Study Appraisal	Domain 4: Synthesis and Findings	Overall Risk of Bias
1	Joel Samu-2025	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
2	Naurin Farooq Khan-2022	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
3	Wesam Fallatah-2024	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
4	Xiaowei Chen-2025	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

Quality Assessment using ROBINS-I Tool

#	Author's name	Bias due to confounding	Bias in selection of participants into the study	Bias in classification of interventions/exposures	Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Bias due to missing data	Bias in measurement of outcomes	Bias in selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
1	Abdulelah A Alshammari-2024	Serious	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
2	Adel Yazdanmehr-2022	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Serious	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
3	Agata McCormac-2018	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
4	A. J. Burns-2019	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
5	Alessandro Pollini-2021	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
6	Alexandra von Preuschen-2024	No information	Moderate	No information	No information	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
7	Al-Shanfari I-2022	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	High	Low	Moderate
8	Cornelia Gerdenitsch-2022	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	No information	Moderate	Low	Moderate
9	Dawn Branley-Bell-2021	No information	Moderate	No information	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
10	Diana Ussher-Eke-2025	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
11	Michael Fagan-2017	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	High	Low	Moderate
12	Filiz Mizrak-2025	Moderate	Moderate	Low	No information	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
13	Hao Chen-2022	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
14	Huigang Liang-2019	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
15	John D'Arcy-2017	Moderate	Moderate	N/A	N/A	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate

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16	Laura M.Bishop-2025	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
17	Lin Chen-2022	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
18	Markus Willing-2021	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
19	Martin Dart-2023	Moderate	Low	Low	Not Applicable	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
20	Mohd Anwar-2016	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
21	Moneer Alshaikh-2021	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
22	Gregory D. Moody-2018	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
23	Muhammad Ali Fauzi-2021	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate	High	Low	Moderate
24	Noor Suhani Sulaiman-2022	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	No information	Moderate	Low	Moderate
25	Paul Benjamin-2023	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low a Moderate
26	Princely Ifinedo-2017	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
27	Prosper K. Yeng-2024	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate
28	Prosper K. Yeng-2021	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
29	Prosper K. Yeng-2022	Moderate	High	Moderate	Not applicable	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
30	Sanja Budimir-2024	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
31	Sanja Budimir-2021	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
32	Sanja Budimir-2021	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
33	Sanjana Sundara -2024	Moderate	Moderate	Low	No Information	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
34	Azadeh Savoli-2017	Low	Low	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Low	Low	Low	Low
35	Scott R. Boss-2015	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
36	Sokratis Nifakos-2021	N/A	N/A	N/A	Low	Low	N/A	Moderate	Moderate
37	Sultan T. Alanazi-2020	Moderate	Moderate	No information	No information	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
38	Nik Thompson-2024	Serious	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
39	AJ Burns-2017	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
40	AJ Burns-2022	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Not Applicable	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
41	Alex Koohang-2020	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
42	Clay Posey-2015	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
43	EunWon Lee-2021	Moderate	Moderate	Low / Not applicable	Low / Not applicable	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate

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44	Gurpreet Dhillon-2020	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
45	Jhon D' Arcy-2019	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
46	Jie Zhen-2021	Moderate	Moderate	N/A	N/A	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
47	John Blythe-2018	Moderate	Serious	N/A	N/A	No information	Moderate	Low	Moderate
48	Joshua Davis-2021	Moderate	Low	Low	N/A	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
49	Kuang-Ming Kuo-2021	Moderate	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
50	Ming-Ling Sher-2016	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
51	Mohammad Jalali-2020	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
52	Ning Yang-2020	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
53	Norshima Humaidi-2017	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
54	Philip Menard-2015	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low a Moderate
55	Princely Ifinedo-2018	Low	Low	Low	N/A	Low	Low	Low	Low
56	Sahar Farshadkhah.-2021	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low a Moderate
57	Teodor Sommestad- 2019	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
58	XU-2020	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
59	XU-2019	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate

Quality Assessment using CASP Tool

#	Author's name	1. Clear research question/aims	2. Appropriate methodology /design	3. Comprehensive search/recruitment	4. Appropriate inclusion/exclusion/selection	5. Quality assessment	6. Data extraction/ synthesis	7. Synthesis of results/findings	8. Conflicts/funding/ethics	9. Applicability/valuable	10. Clear implications/limitations	Overall Risk of Bias
1	A. Reeves-2021	Low	Moderate	High	Moderate	High	High	Low	–	Low	Low	Moderate
2	Abdulelah Alshammari-2024	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	–	Low	Low	Moderate
3	Afrah Almansoori-2023	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	High	Low	Low	Low	–	–	Moderate
4	Alexandra von Preuschen-2023	Low	Low	Low	Low / Unclear	High	Low	Low	–	Low	Low	Moderate
5	Arash Ghazvini-2017	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High	Low	Moderate	High	Low	Low	Moderate

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#	Author's name	1. Clear research question/aims	2. Appropriate methodology/design	3. Comprehensive search/recruitment	4. Appropriate inclusion/exclusion/selection	5. Quality assessment	6. Data extraction/synthesis	7. Synthesis of results/findings	8. Conflicts/funding/ethics	9. Applicability/valuable	10. Clear implications/limitations	Overall Risk of Bias
6	Calvin NOBLES-2022	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Not Applicable	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Unclear	Low	–	Moderate
7	Carlo Pugnetti-2024	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	–	Moderate
8	Debby Bouma-2025	Low	Low	Moderate	–	Moderate	–	Low	Low	High	Low	Moderate
9	Hana Yousuf Zainal-2022	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
10	Ilkka Tikanmäki-2025	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
11	Jamila Djumabaeva-2025	Low	Moderate	High	High	Moderate-High	High	Moderate	Unclear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
12	Jason A. Williams-2024	Low	Low/Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	–	Moderate
13	Jie Zhen-2020	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	–	Moderate	–	Moderate
14	Julia Prummer-2024	Low	Low	Low	Low	High	Moderate	Low	–	Low	Low	Moderate
15	Kalam Khadka-2025	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	High	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
16	Kitty Kioskli-2023	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	–	Moderate
17	Judith Kraushaar-2025	Low	High	High	Moderate	Moderate	N/A	Moderate	–	High	Moderate	Moderate to high
18	Mada Alassaf-2021	Low	Low	Low	Low	Medium	Medium	Low	–	Low	–	Moderate
19	Peter Mayer -2017	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low-Moderate	Low	Low	–	–	–	Low a Moderate
20	Prosper K. Yeng-2021	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear/Moderate	Low	Low	–	Low	Low	Low
21	Prosper K. Yeng-2022	Low	Low	Unclear	Unclear	High	Low	Low	–	–	–	Moderate
22	Prosper K. Yeng-2022	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
23	Puspita Kencana Sari-2022	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	High	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	–	Moderate
24	Rachid Lahcen-2020	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High	High	Low	Low	Low	–	–	Moderate to high
25	Sanja Budimir-2022	Low	Low	Moderate	High	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
26	Sunil Chaudhary-2024	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	–	Moderate
27	Sunil Chaudhary-2022	Low	Low	Unclear	High	High	Low	Low	–	Low	Unclear	Moderate
28	Daeun Lee-2023	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Serious	Moderate	Low	Unclear	Low	Serious	Moderate to high
29	Michael Foth-2015	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Acceptable	–	Applicable	Clear	Moderate